

New Copper(II) Azino Complexes

AKILA A. SALEH

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Education, Ain Shams University, Roxy, Cairo, Egypt

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As part of a systematic study of Cu^{II}-azino complexes¹, we have prepared six new Cu^{II}-Schiff base complexes. An investigation of the effect of varying the ligands (1a-c and 2a-c) on the structure and properties of the complexes has also been attempted.

1a-c

2a-c

Results and Discussion

The results of elemental analyses of the Cu^{II} complexes of the azino ligands (Table 1) indicate the stoichiometry of the complexes to be 1 : 1 (M : L) and 1 : 2 (M : L). The molar conductance for complexes with ligands 1c and 2a indicates the non-coordinated nature of the SO₄ group.

The TGA data for [Cu(HBAEC)₂.2H₂O], [Cu(HMBAEB).2H₂O]SO₄.4H₂O and [Cu(HBAMDC)_n] lead to the following conclusions : (i) crystal lattice water molecules are initially volatilised in the temperature range 55–80°, (ii) the water molecules contributing to complex formation are lost at 150–240°, indicating that these molecules are coordinated to the central metal ion, and the number of water molecules determined from the thermograms confirms the data obtained by elemental analyses, and (iii) the Cu^{II} complexes are unstable above 250° and CuO being

finally obtained in the range 375–450°.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis% : Found/(Calcd.)			
	C	H	N	Cu
[Cu(HBAEC) ₂ .2H ₂ O]	47.29 (47.20)	3.90 4.00	11.03 11.08	12.51 12.45
[Cu(MHBAEC) ₂ (EtOH) ₂].2EtOH	52.70 (52.30)	5.40 5.40	9.46 10.40	10.73 10.53
[Cu(BAEC).2H ₂ O] ₂ SO ₄ .8H ₂ O	39.71 (39.10)	4.90 3.50	5.90 6.30	13.13 13.45
[Cu(HMBAEB).2H ₂ O]SO ₄ .4H ₂ O	44.39 (44.20)	4.35 4.20	6.09 6.02	6.90 7.40
[Cu(HBAEB) ₂].5H ₂ O	53.80 (54.00)	4.76 5.00	7.80 8.20	8.89 8.75
[Cu(HBAMDC) _n]	61.80 (62.00)	3.90 4.10	6.87 7.20	15.58 15.23

The ir spectra of each solid complex under investigation exhibit a broad band around 3 350–3 400 cm⁻¹ (OH) which is attributed to water and/or ethanol molecules associated with the complex formation. The new bands observed at 920–970 and 620–665 cm⁻¹ which are absent in the spectra of the free ligands, are attributed to ν_{HO} and ω_{HO} of the coordinated water molecules. The spectra of the dehydrated metal chelates show the disappearance of the ν_{HO} phenolic or alcoholic and δ_{C-OH} bands observed at 3 300–3 195 and 1 285–1 275 cm⁻¹ respectively, in the spectra of the free ligands. This indicates the bonding of the metal ions to the ligands through a covalent linkage with the oxygen of the phenolic or alcoholic group. The bands at 1 608–1 600 cm⁻¹ corresponding to the azomethine ν_{C=N} of the free ligands shift to lower frequency on complex formation by 30–54 cm⁻¹, hence the nitrogen atom of the azomethine group coordinates to the metal complexes of ligands 1a, 1c, 2a and 2c. The appearance of two bands, 1 600–1 608 and 1 550–1 555 cm⁻¹ respectively, in the spectra of the complexes of ligands 1b and 2b, is due to free and coordinated C=N because one ligand coordinates to the metal through nitrogen of the azomethine and the other ligand is not coordinated through nitrogen of the azomethine. The ν_{Cu-O} and ν_{Cu-N} bands for all the complexes are observed at 485–525 and 440–465 cm⁻¹. The ν₃ and ν₁ (S-O) bands of the complexes of ligands 1c and 2a are observed at 1 100–1 295 and 900 cm⁻¹ respectively.

The electronic spectra of all the Cu^{II} complexes of azino

compounds have in general four bands at (372–393) and (363–376), (422–517) and (417–435), (574–639) and (539–578), and (704–739) and (650–700) in DMF and nujol mull respectively. The first band is assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ within the ligands, i.e. within the C=O and the second to $\pi-\pi^*$ of C=N, the third and fourth bands are due to CT from (L \rightarrow Cu) as a result of complex formation which can be assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ transitions respectively. This may indicate that ligands 1a, 1c, 2a and 2c possess distorted octahedral geometry around Cu²⁺ leading to square-planar arrangement² and 1b possessing tetragonally distorted octahedral while ligand 2b square-pyramidal coordination of Cu^{II} in dimeric azino complexes³.

Magnetic moment data (1.0–1.48 B.M.) which are below the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.) for mononuclear Cu^{II} complexes, seem to confirm the planar coordination, since planar Cu^{II} complexes are inclined to the metal-metal interaction along the axial positions which is in agreement with the previous results⁴.

Experimental

All commercial grade chemicals were distilled/crystallised before use. The ligands (1a-c and 2a-c) were prepared by the reported method⁵.

The complexes were prepared by adding ethanolic solution (50 ml) of the ligand (2 mmol) to aqueous solution (50 ml) of copper(II) sulphate. The colour of the solution changed from gray-yellow to green-blue after stirring for 4 h, then the volume was reduced to 20 ml. The resulting green solids after adding ether were crystallised from ethanol-ether, washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure (yields 65–70%). Physical measurements were done as reported earlier⁶.

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